

Infertility in Women of Reproductive Age: Association of Thyroid Hormones with FSH, LH, and Prolactin

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Abstract:

Background: The estimated prevalence of infertility ranges from 12 to 14 percent. Thus, it is a prevalent ailment with significant psychological, physical, and financial ramifications. In order to properly assess these illnesses, a multifaceted diagnostic strategy is required. Thyroid hormones, FSH, LH, and prolactin were correlated with infertility in women of reproductive age in this present study. Aim of this study was to correlate thyroid hormones with FSH, LH and prolactin in infertility in the reproductive age group women.

Methods: Between the ages of 19 and 45, a total of 60 infertile women and 40 healthy, fertile women volunteers were chosen based on OPD. Twenty of the 60 infertile women had secondary infertility, while 40 had original infertility. They underwent Chemiluminescence Immunoassay (CLIA) to check their thyroid hormone levels.

Result: There was a positive correlation between TSH and prolactin. Additionally, they had a negative correlation with T3, FSH, and LH in infertile groups. Thus, we can conclude that hypothyroidism and hyperprolactinemia are important factors in the etiopathogenesis of infertility. Chronic hypothyroidism can lead to hyperprolactinemia and ovulatory dysfunction.

Conclusion: Therefore, it may be very beneficial to detect and treat hypothyroidism early on, before ovulatory dysfunction and hyperprolactinemia manifest. In order to identify subclinical thyroid issues and reduce the risk of infertility, TSH screening should be performed on all women in the early reproductive age range.

Keywords: Infertility, Thyroid hormones, FSH, LH, Prolactin, Chemiluminescence, Hypothyroidism etc.

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Introduction

Hormonal abnormalities of the female reproductive system include a variety of issues that arise from the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis malfunctioning. Infertility is frequently caused by these somewhat common conditions. [1] Most people have plans for their futures that include having children, and becoming a parent is undoubtedly one of the most commonly desired adult aspirations. But not every couple who wants a child will get one on their own, and others will require medical assistance to address underlying infertility issues. Globally, infertility is acknowledged as a public health concern. [2]

During their reproductive years, many people may experience infertility. They could not be aware that they are infertile. Numerous factors, including age, lifestyle, and physical issues, are listed as causes of infertility. The infertility problem is more common phenomenon among the women now days and has

increased over past 30 years. [3] Between 12 and 14 percent of people are thought to be infertile. Thus, it is a prevalent ailment with significant medical, financial, and psychological ramifications. [4] For these illnesses to be properly evaluated, a multifaceted diagnostic approach is required.

To improve the entry of non-growing follicles into the growth phase, [5] pituitary chemicals like TSH, prolactin, or growth hormone may work in concert with FSH and LH. Increased prolactin production in hypothyroidism may result in morphological abnormalities in the follicles, which may inhibit gonadotropin secretion and function. Normal ovulatory function and prolactin levels are also restored by adequate thyroid supplementation. [7] Since thyroid hormones may be required for the maximum generation of both progesterone and estradiol, hypothyroidism alone may contribute to infertility even in the absence of

hyperprolactinemia. [8] The hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis and the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis have been linked in clinical and experimental research.

FSH is frequently employed as a measure of ovarian function since it promotes the formation of follicles in the ovaries. Poor follicle growth and, as a result, anovulatory cycles are indicated by elevated FSH levels. Hyperprolactinemia [9] may be indicated by decreased FSH levels.

Ovulation occurs within 48 hours after the LH surge around day 12, which causes the ovary to release the ovum. Ovarian dysfunction may be indicated by elevated LH levels. Hyperprolactinemia [9] may be indicated by decreased LH levels.

Although there is a connection between gonadotropins and thyroid hormones, the association between serum gonadotropins and thyroid hormones has received very little attention. This study, "correlation of thyroid hormones with FSH, LH, and prolactin in infertility in the reproductive age group women," was therefore carried out.

Material and Methods

From March 2024 to August of 2024, this cross-sectional study was carried out at Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar. All biochemical investigations done at Biochemistry department of DMCH. Infertile and normal fertile women age between 19 to 45 years were included in this study. Women who were male factor infertility, who received medication that could alter TFT (amiodarone and phenytoin excluding β -

blockers, heparin & dopamine), female factors were tubal factor, any congenital anomaly of the urogenital tract, or any obvious organic lesion and any history of thyroid disease or previous thyroid surgery were excluded in this study.

Following written and informed consent, 40 participants who were normally fertile and 60 infertile women between the ages of 19 and 45 were chosen on the basis of OPD. Twenty of the 60 infertile women had secondary infertility, while 40 had original infertility.

A thorough history, a clinical examination, and laboratory testing were used to choose the participants. Participants' age, menstrual history, obstetric history, history of medications, and history of addictions were all thoroughly recorded.

Biochemical Investigations:

After written informed consent, 12 hour fasting venous blood samples were collected from all participants in their early follicular phase of menstrual cycle i.e. between days 3th to 5th in plane bulbs. Serum was separated after 1 hour by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, and was tested for following parameters.

1. Serum FT3
2. Serum FT4
3. Serum TSH
4. Serum FSH
5. Serum LH
6. Serum Prolactin

Results

Quantitative estimation of all hormones done by Chemiluminescence Immunoassay (CLIA) using Acculite CLIA micro wells.

Table 1: Showing number of study subjects and their groups

Group	Subjects	Number (n)
I	Infertile women (cases)	60
II	Normal fertile women (control)	40

Table 2: Showing number of subgroups in group I

Group	Subjects	Number (n)
IA	Primary Infertile women	40
IIB	Secondary Infertile women	20

Table 3: The mean age distribution of subjects

Variable	Group IA (n=40)	Group IB (n=20)	Group II (Control) (n=40)
Age	23.525±2.48	27.575±1.94	27.0±2.12

Table 4: Hormonal status in the cases and controls

	Cases (n=60)			Controls (n=40)		
	Euthyroid	Hyperthyroid	Hypothyroid	Euthyroid	Hyperthyroid	Hypothyroid
FT3(pg/ml)	2.34±0.8	5.2±0.55	1.1±0.2	2.8±0.23	5.05±0.31	1.01±0.14
FT4(ng/ml)	1.5±0.4	3.2±0.64	0.66±0.07	1.4±0.89	3.1±0.33	0.45±0.11
TSH(\square IU/L)	3.9±1.6*	0.24±0.05	8.72±0.79**	3.36±0.8	0.17±0.4	6.86±0.45
Prolactin(ng/ml)	30.9±17***	16.01±1.06**	77±9***	13.6±6.09	8.1±3.2	29.7±2.01
LH(IU/L)	6.02±2.7***	6.5±1.29**	3.34±1.0***	8.2±2.04	7.39±0.85	9.9±2
FSH(IU/L)	4.1±2.64**	3.6±0.75**	3.44±2.08***	6.7±1.6	6.19±1.01	10.38±1.3

*P<0.5, **p<0.01 and ***p<0.001 in comparing the distributions to the respective group in controls.

Thyroid function status in the study population is presented in table 4. Cases and control further divided in Euthyroid, Hyperthyroid & hypothyroid according to their thyroid hormones status. Most of the infertile women 47/60 (78.33%) and control 34/60 (85%) were euthyroid. The prevalence of hyperthyroidism in the cases and the controls were 3/60 (5%) and 3/40 (7.5%), respectively.

Hypothyroidism was seen in 11/60 (18%) of the infertile women whereas in the control group it was found to be 3/40 (7.5%). The crude prevalence of hypothyroidism was higher when compared to hyperthyroidism in the infertile group. Significantly higher serum TSH levels were noted in the infertile cases with euthyroid ($p < 0.5$) and hypothyroidism ($p < 0.01$) when their distributions were compared to

their respective control groups. The rise in serum FT4 and FT3 in the infertile group with hyperthyroidism was found to be non-significant as compared to the control group with hyperthyroidism.

The mean serum prolactin concentration in the infertile cases with euthyroid was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) than the control group with euthyroid. The infertile women with hypothyroidism had significantly higher prolactin levels than the other three groups (the controls and the infertile subjects with euthyroid and hyperthyroidism) ($p < 0.001$). There is also higher level of prolactin in hypothyroid control as compared to euthyroid and hyperthyroid control.

Table 5: Hyperprolactinemia and Hypothyroidism in study groups

Parameters	Control	Primary Infertility	Secondary infertility
Hyperprolactinemia	3	22	5
Hypothyroidism	3	7	5

Serum prolactin levels > 25 ng/ml. (Ref. range: 2 – 25) were observed in

- 3/40 participants in control (7.5%),
- 22/40 participants in primary infertile (55%) and
- 5/20 participants in sec. infertile (25%)

Serum TSH levels > 6.16 μ U/ml. (Ref. range: 0.39 – 6.16) were observed in

- 3/40 participants in control (7.5%),
- 7/40 participants in primary infertile (17.5%) and
- 5/20 participants in sec. infertile (22.5%)

Out of 27 hyperprolactinemic infertile women 11 are hypothyroid therefore incidence of hypothyroidism in hyperprolactinemic infertile women is 40.7%.

Table 6: Correlation coefficients (r value) in Primary Infertility

	TSH	T4	T3	FSH	LH
Prolactin	$r=0.95^*$ $P=0.00$	-0.59 7.8	-0.68 3.5	-0.20 0.07	-0.62 6.7
LH	$r=-0.60$ $P=3.2$	0.18* 0.002	0.21* 0.000	0.45* 0.000	
FSH	$r=-0.14$ $P=0.203$	0.017 0.87	-0.05 0.60		
FT3	$r=-0.76$ $P=2.7$	0.78 4.84			
FT4	$r=-0.69$ $P=9.01$				

Prolactin is negatively correlated with all parameters except TSH which shows positive correlation.

Prolactin and TSH shows strong positive correlation with each other. ($r = 0.95$) ($P = 0.000$).

TSH also shows negative correlation with all parameters. LH show positive correlation with FT3 and FT4. LH also shows strong positive correlation with FSH ($r = 0.45$) ($P = 0.00$).

Discussion

The purpose of the current study was to examine the relationship between thyroid status and serum

prolactin, LH, and FSH in infertile women. The participants were split into two groups based on fertility: Group I consisted of infertile women (cases), and Group II consisted of normal, healthy, and fertile women (controls). Cases are further subdivided into two categories: Group IA, which consists of primary infertile women, and Group IB, which consists of secondary infertile women.

Thyroid hormones are known to affect sexual development and reproductive function in both sexes. If left untreated, hypothyroidism from infancy results in sexual immaturity, and hypothyroidism that starts before puberty delays

the development of puberty and anovulatory cycles. According to many textbooks, hypothyroidism in adult women causes variations in the duration of their cycles and the amount of bleeding they experience.

It is well established that thyroid dysfunction lowers the chance of becoming pregnant and negatively impacts the outcome of pregnancy. There is still a lack of information regarding the connection between thyroid conditions and infertility, and the relationship with a specific cause of infertility has not been fully examined [11].

Increases in prolactin secretion can be pathogenic (caused by hypothalamic and pituitary disorders), physiological (during pregnancy and lactation), or iatrogenic. Amenorrhea and irregular ovulation are caused by hyperprolactinemia, which also suppresses the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis and makes the ovary resistant to the effects of gonadotropin.

Serum Prolactin & Thyroid profile

1. Serum levels of Prolactin and TSH increased in infertile women as compared to control, the differences among three groups being highly significant ($P < 0.001$).
2. Serum Prolactin levels were found to be strongly correlated with TSH levels in primary infertile women and Secondary infertile women ($r = 0.95$ and 0.74 respectively) and this correlation was statistically significant ($P < 0.001$).
3. As per the study, we observed a greater percentage of infertile women with hypothyroidism exhibiting hyperprolactinemia (40.7%).

These findings in our study strongly correlate with the findings of study by Goswami Binita et al [1], they found 46.1% infertile women with hypothyroidism had hyperprolactinemia. Kumkum et al [10], in their study incidence of hypothyroidism in hyperprolactinemic women was 25.50% (13/51). So, a positive correlation of 1:4 was found between hypothyroidism and hyperprolactinemia. Affia Tasneem et al [11], in their study measured Serum Prolactin and TSH levels in 1365 patients (46 males, 1319 females). They found 33% hypothyroid in hyperprolactinemic patients. Mechanism whereby hypothyroidism associate with hyperprolactinemia can be as follows:-

In hypothyroidism there is increase TSH and Prolactin levels and produce pituitary enlargement, these alterations are mainly produced by the high levels of TRH induced by the decreased negative feedback of thyroid hormones at the hypothalamic-pituitary level. TRH stimulates the secretion of both TSH and Prolactin producing hypertrophy and hyperplasia of TSH and Prolactin secreting cells. In hypothyroidism the number and sensitivity of TRH

receptors increases in the thyrotrope and the lactotrope. TSH and Prolactin responses to TRH are also increased. [12]

It may be postulated that hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis in such infertile women is less sensitive and they had compensated thyroid hormone profile with tissue hypothyroidism. Such thyroid under-function can affect female reproductive physiology indirectly in a number of ways:

1. Altering the pituitary ovarian axis.
2. Decreasing the binding activity of sex hormone binding globulin (SHBG) resulting in increased free testosterone and estradiol.
3. Decreasing the metabolic clearance of androstenedione and estrone.
4. It also increases TRH levels resulting in increased prolactin levels.
5. A delayed LH response to LH-releasing hormone.

Generally measurement of serum TSH in infertile women is employed for detection of hypothyroidism. TSH is an important hormone to access thyroid function but its normal range (usually 0.3-6.0 $\mu\text{IU/L}$) is wide. A limitation with its laboratory determination is that it cannot detect tissue hypothyroidism. Recent laboratory guidelines from the National Academy of Clinical Biochemistry indicate that more than 95% of normal individuals have TSH level below 2.5 $\mu\text{IU}/80$. The remainder, those with higher values is likely to have Hashimoto thyroiditis or other causes of elevated TSH.

Concluding points about relationship between Prolactin & Thyroid profile:

- There was a strong positive correlation between Prolactin and TSH levels and the correlation was statistically significant. ($P < 0.001$). Therefore hypothyroidism can be suggested as a surrogate marker of hyperprolactinemia.
- Prolactin showed negative correlation with FT3 & FT4 levels in infertility.

LH and FSH

In our study serum LH & FSH was decreased in infertile women as compared to control, the differences among three groups being highly significant ($P < 0.001$). LH & FSH both are negatively correlated with prolactin.

K. Mohan and Mazher Sultana [13], in their study of 70 women, found lower level of serum FSH in infertile women were when compared to control groups, difference being statistically significant ($P < 0.001$). Serum LH concentration was lower in the infertile group than in the control group ($P < 0.001$).

Azima Kalsum, Samina Jalali [14], in their study shows a significant decrease in serum LH in follicular, ovulatory and luteal phase in hyperprolactinemic women having primary and secondary infertility. Significantly ($P < 0.05$) low serum FSH levels were observed in ovulatory phase in women reported with primary infertility. Similarly significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in serum FSH in luteal phase in hyperprolactinemic women reported with secondary infertility was observed.

Yamaguchi et al [15], found decreased LH secretion in nocturnal hyperprolactinemic women.

Mc Neilly A.S [16], showed similar association between increased level of prolactin and a reduction in both LH and FSH during infertility in women with pathological hyperprolactinemia.

According to the current study, infertile women's blood prolactin and TSH levels increased proportionately while their T3, T4, LH, and FSH levels decreased. Prolactin and TSH showed a strong positive association. As prolactin increased, LH and FSH decreased.

Long-term primary hypothyroidism-induced hyperprolactinemia has been linked to a variety of ovulatory dysfunctions, from moderately enhanced corpus luteal progesterone secretion to oligomenorrhea or amenorrhea when circulating prolactin levels are high. Hypothyroidism causes amenorrhea because of suppression of both FSH and LH, as well as hyperprolactinemia brought on by a malfunction in the positive feedback of estrogen on LH. In the infertile group, our study found a strong correlation between irregular menstruation patterns and hypothyroidism and hyperprolactinemia ($p < 0.001$).

For these reasons, TSH and prolactin are commonly-ordered clinical tests in evaluating infertile women.

Since the study was conducted in a hospital and recruiting counterparting controls was challenging, we only enrolled 40 controls in our study compared to 60 cases because of the strict inclusion criteria and non-compliance. Carefully extrapolating the results to the general population is necessary to prevent even the smallest indications of selection bias. To better determine the desired prevalence, a population-based study could be carried out. As it was a cross sectional study, we cannot infer conclusions about cause and effect relationship between infertility and hypothyroidism as well as hyperprolactinemia.

In order to better manage infertility cases, all of the aforementioned findings must be confirmed in a larger, well-systematized study with a large number of control subjects (volunteers) and a lengthy follow-up period. This will help to validate the variation in TSH and prolactin levels and to

elucidate the cause of the higher prevalence of hyperprolactinemia in hypothyroidism.

This study may be extended as prospective follow up study by giving thyroxin supplement to all infertile women with hypothyroidism and hyperprolactinemia.

To determine which patients have hyperprolactinemia due to hypothyroidism, a thyroid function test, particularly TSH, is advised for each hyperprolactinemic patient. Maternal hypothyroidism, subclinical hypothyroidism, and female hypothyroidism should all be thoroughly investigated as secondary causes of hyperprolactinemia. Additionally, research on hypothyroidism and iodine deficiency disorder (IDD) and their connections to infertility should be conducted.

Conclusion

The current study involved 100 women who were divided into three categories based on their fertility: primary infertile, secondary infertile, and normal fertile (control). Our work's idea was to measure each participant's thyroid profile, prolactin, LH, and FSH levels and correlate them with one another.

There was a positive correlation between TSH and prolactin. Additionally, they had a negative correlation with T3, FSH, and LH in infertile groups. Thus, we can conclude that hypothyroidism and hyperprolactinemia are important factors in the etiopathogenesis of infertility.

Considering primary and secondary infertility both had higher levels of serum prolactin and TSH as compared to control. Prolactin is significantly high in primary infertility as compared to secondary infertility while TSH values were slightly high in secondary infertility. LH, FSH, T3 & T4 values were low in infertile as compared to fertile, but among primary and secondary infertility their values not differ.

Both hypothyroidism and hyperprolactinemia may result in menstrual disorders. Oligomenorrhoea was most common in infertile women. Hypothyroidism is commonly associated with hyperprolactinemia and such patients exhibit ovulatory failure. Hence, assessment of serum TSH and prolactin levels are mandatory in the work up of all infertile women, especially those presenting with menstrual irregularities. Although hypothyroid individuals tend to be hyperprolactinemic, and causes infertility, the most fundamental fact is that, not all infertile women are hypothyroid, nor do they all have hyperprolactinemia.

So the basic approach should be to identify those hypothyroid individuals who have

hyperprolactinemia and are at greatest risk for the development of infertility.

Those infertile women with normal levels of thyroid hormones may not necessarily indicate the true status of thyroid hormones in the body. All those infertile women with concurrent normal levels of thyroid hormones may still be having subclinical thyroid problem which may be responsible for infertility.

Long standing hypothyroidism may develop ovulatory dysfunction, and hyperprolactinemia. So identifying and treating hypothyroidism at an earlier stage before the appearance of ovulatory dysfunction and hyperprolactinemia, can have potentially great preventive value. So TSH screening of all females of early reproductive age group should be done so as to detect subclinical thyroid problem and to prevent infertility risk.

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